

51

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3. FIVE YEAR TREND OF GROSS ALPHA/BETA ACTIVITY IN DRINKING WATER FROM VOJVODINA REGION

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Objectives: Gross alpha/beta analyses are widely used as the first step of the radiological characterization of drinking water safety. Screening levels have been set to 0.5 Bq/ l and 1 Bq/l for gross alpha/beta activity, respectively. The objective was to determine the concentration and trends of gross alpha/beta radioactivity in five-year period in drinking water from the settlements in Vojvodina region (APV).

Materials and methods: The 323 drinking water samples were taken true 2012-2016 in 99 settlements of APV by IPHV. Simultaneous measurement of gross alpha/beta activities was done in accredited laboratory of UNS by liquid scintillation counting technique. The average values of gross beta activity were established by determination, because in 73% samples they were below the laboratory limit value. For statistical analyses linear trend line, ANOVA and Pearson correlation were used.

Results: The average value of gross alpha/beta activity was 0.09 ± 0.14 Bq/l / 0.221 ± 0.13 Bq/l, minimum <0.005 Bq/l / <0.03 Bq/l and maximum 1.20 Bq/l / 0.94 Bq/l, respectively. In five controlled samples the gross alpha/beta radioactivity were above the national limit values (NLV), however the activity of radionuclide (^{226}Ra , ^{232}Th and ^{137}Cs) were not above the NLV. Linear trend of the average and minimum values of the gross alpha/beta activity was negative, confirmed by the ANOVA (for gross alpha: $F=10.06$, $p<0.01$ and for gross beta: $F=65.50$, $p<0.01$). The linear trend of the gross beta activity maximum values showed an increase ($R^2 = 0.59$). Pearson's coefficient of correlation revealed a statistically significant positive correlation ($r = 0.249$, $p < 0.001$) between gross alpha/beta activity.

Conclusion: Although in the five year period the average concentrations of gross alpha/beta activity in drinking water are below the NLV, the increased linear trend of the maximum values for gross beta activity, as well as exceeded gross alpha/beta activity in five samples, point the importance of continuous monitoring of drinking water in order to minimize possible risks for human health.

Keywords: Water, drinking; Water Pollutants, Radioactive; Environment and Public Health